

Figure S1. Forest plot of univariable mendelian randomization studies exploring associations between iron deficiency anemia to autoimmune diseases.

Table S1 Sensitivity analysis, heterogeneity, and pleiotropy, investigating MR assumption violation.

Exposure	Heterogeneity tests							Test for directional horizontal pleiotropy						
	I2	Inverse variance weighted			MR Egger			Egger_intercept	pval	MR-PRESSO	MR-PRESSO	MR-PRESSO		
		Q	Q_df	Q_pval	Q	Q_df	Q_pval					pval	Outlier SNPs	
AH	33.87%	9.072	6	0.170	8.789	5	0.118	-0.013	0.033	0.705	0.293	NA	NA	NA
Asthma	0.89%	108.969	108	0.456	108.963	107	0.429	0.000	0.006	0.937	0.460	NA	NA	NA
CD	0.00%	72.008	79	0.698	67.949	78	0.785	0.014	0.007	0.047	0.707	NA	NA	NA
IBD	40.40%	25.166	15	0.048	24.456	14	0.040	0.012	0.018	0.534	0.061	NA	NA	NA
IBS	0	1.892	3	0.595	1.099	2	0.577	0.114	0.128	0.467	0.623	NA	NA	NA
MS	0	1.725	4	0.786	1.704	3	0.636	0.006	0.039	0.895	0.768	NA	NA	NA
PsA	20.56%	8.090	4	0.088	5.161	3	0.160	-0.056	0.043	0.283	0.213	NA	NA	NA
RA	0.00%	7.491	12	0.824	7.343	11	0.771	-0.004	0.011	0.708	0.865	NA	NA	NA
T1D	7.93%	16.293	15	0.363	15.428	14	0.350	-0.009	0.010	0.391	0.400	NA	NA	NA
UC	21.25%	8.888	7	0.261	8.304	6	0.217	0.015	0.023	0.540	0.280	NA	NA	NA
SLE	23.76%	53.778	41	0.087	52.624	40	0.087	0.009	0.010	0.355	0.095	NA	NA	NA
PSC	3.78%	17.668	17	0.410	15.350	16	0.499	0.018	0.011	0.147	0.407	NA	NA	NA
CeD	9.71%	40.979	37	0.300	40.659	36	0.273	-0.003	0.006	0.597	0.323	NA	NA	NA
PBC	0	11.864	21	0.943	10.387	20	0.961	0.011	0.009	0.238	0.946	NA	NA	NA

